

When and How Elections Drive Conflict Transformation: Transitional Justice and Peacebuilding in WANA Societies

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This short intervention will examine the conditions under which elections can be conducive to conflict transformation. This paper builds on my own observations of elections in Algeria and Tunisia and the electoral analysis published by the Observatory of Politics and Elections in the Arab and Muslim World (OPEMAM). I focus on four comparable cases from West Asia and North Africa (WANA): Algeria (2002-); Tunisia (2011-); Sudan (2005-); and Jordan (1989-).

In general terms, elections may have a double sword effect on conflicts, either aggravating existing divides and cleavages or reducing them. They can foster social peace through power sharing or act as catalyst of conflict (EC-UNDP-IDEA 2011, 7).

Massive violations of human rights, whether committed during armed conflicts or under authoritarian regimes, are central to the UN framework of transitional justice, conceived and developed in the United Nations Secretary-General UN SG 2004 Report, titled “The Rule of Law and Transitional Justice in Conflict and Post-conflict Societies: Report of the Secretary-General,” and the 2010 UN SG Guidance Note.

Within this framework, institutional reform is a crucial component aimed at preventing the recurrence of atrocities (UN. Secretary-General 2010, 2). Institutional reform encompasses, among other things, electoral design, constitutional design, and the legal bases for a political party structure. Notwithstanding the significant impact of elections on conflict, only a scant body of literature has examined the positive effects they may have on peacebuilding efforts and transitional justice.

Methodology

To trace the effects of elections on transitional justice, I propose a double analytical tool. My analytical tool departs from the transdisciplinary field of transitional justice and puts political science in dialogue with International Relations.

First, I underscore the significance of contexts in shaping the outcomes and the effects of elections. As Thomas Hansen puts it, “operating with a single theory of transitional justice is problematic” (2011, 3). I, thus, distinguish between regime change and non-regime change cases, as well as whether the country has undergone a previous armed

conflict, authoritarian rule, or both.

Tunisia stands out as the only case of successful political transition without previous armed conflict, whereas Algeria and Sudan both experienced authoritarianism, armed conflict, but not regime transition. Finally, Jordan had a repressive rule, but it did not experience significant armed conflict or regime change.

Second, I emphasize the key role of inclusive processes within post-conflict and post-authoritarian transitions. Statistical evidence links the sustainability of peace agreements to the participation and inclusion of all groups, particularly minorities and women (Nils-son 2012). Also, the Women Peace Security Agenda (WPS) has since its inception strongly reinforced the significant benefit of including women's groups in ensuring successful conflict resolution.

With all of this in mind, I suggest that elections may produce inclusion and facilitate peacebuilding at two different levels: elite inclusion/exclusion and social inclusion. A dynamic two-level analysis is used to show that each of the four cases follows a different pattern. That is elite and social inclusion may operate quite autonomously from each other.

Constitutional Design, Elections, and Social Cleavages

Elections must be understood as part and parcel of political and constitutional design, it creates the architecture of political parties' formation, citizens participation, and political representation. They ensure the functioning and the legitimacy of the legislative, executive, and judicial powers. By elections, the reference here is to all aspects of the legal

electoral framework, from census and voter registration to adjudication of electoral disputes.

Elections and its processes are thus important tools for peacebuilding in post-conflict and post-repression situations, although sometimes with unintended consequences (see for instance Reilly 2008, 2016). They can serve as inclusive instruments, allowing for integration of former enemies, fighting groups, and formerly excluded oppositional forces and minority groups. However, they can also act as tool to exclude agents of the former regime who are responsible for mass atrocities. That is, elections can function as an important vetting tool to exclude former public officials and candidates, as it was widely the case in post-Communist Central and Eastern Europe (Roman 2006). Decisions over how to organize elections, who is allowed to run for elections, and who is excluded from the electoral process produce important effects on the representation, legitimacy, and fairness of the entire political process. It can either reinforce or reduce social cleavages and fractures.

Findings

My findings show that Jordan stands as a case where there has been partial integration of the Palestinian population and partial integration of Palestinian elites (see Dynamic A in FIGURE 1). Dynamic A refers to partial integration of excluded population and partial integration of elites. When a pluralistic system was installed in 1989, they carefully designed a political and electoral system whereby Palestinians (and their political parties) would always have very limited access to political institutions. The electoral system included the overrepresentation of rural districts and tribal sectors and diminished the prospects of political parties and urban

candidates—as they could mobilize constituencies of Palestinian origin.

Dynamic B represents the partial social inclusion and the full elite inclusion, it is the model that best fits the Sudanese case. Following the 2005 Comprehensive Peace Agreement (CPA), the regime and the Southern elites involved in the Second Sudanese Civil War participated in the process leading to the national referendum of independence. All social groups, however, could not be fully incorporated or invited to participate, neither in Sudan nor in South Sudan. The failure to include different groups was a result of state fragility and its weak enforcement capacity.

The case of Tunisia and its troubled path to transitional justice is best understood by applying Dynamic C (see FIGURE 1). Dynamic C refers to the full social inclusion and the partial elite exclusion. In the case of Tunisia,

the full social inclusion combined with partial elite exclusion resulted in favorable political outcomes but hindered the path to transitional justice. Even though the Ben Ali's regime deployed for years a massive apparatus of vigilance and denunciation, only the top officials were taken to trial, and a small fraction of party and state officials were nominally excluded from politics through a process of nominal vetting.

Finally, the Algerian case better corresponds to Dynamic D (see FIGURE 1). Dynamic D refers to the full social inclusion and full elite exclusion. In the case of Algeria, the country witnessed the full inclusion of social groups coupled with the full exclusion of Islamist former political elites. The voters and sympathizers of the Front of Islamic Salvation (FIS)

party could fully participate in elections, but top officials and FIS founders remained excluded from the political process.

Conclusion

The analysis above underscores how elections are strongly connected to transitional justice and conflict transformation, either as foundational events or as series of iterative acts. However, to determine how and when elections can help peacebuilding efforts in post-conflict and post-authoritarian contexts, we need to carefully examine in each case the two-level dynamics of integration and exclusion, from both the elite and grass-root perspectives. This exercise allows us to identify which electoral elements were unsuccessful or could have been better designed to advance the goals of conflict reconciliation.

Constitutional and electoral design, including party laws can be seen as key elements affecting the different inclusion/exclusion dynamics. In Jordan, the electoral system failed to fully integrate the minority and oppositional forces. Also, the constitutional powers vested in the king impeded a more inclusive reform. In Sudan, the constitutional and electoral design could have enabled a democratic post-secession scenario had the Northern elites accepted to stop extracting resources and rent-seeking patronage. In Algeria, the new political elites excluded banned Islamist elites such as the FIS with excessive zeal slamming the door to any possible reconciliation. Finally, in Tunisia the electoral design's goal to minimize the weight of the Islamists had an unintended consequence: Secular and Islamist elites could not agree on a common course to apply transitional justice. Unintentionally, elections debilitated reconciliation and social cohesion, where they were meant to facilitate them.

FIGURE 1: REPRESENTATION OF TWO-LEVEL INCLUSION-EXCLUSION DYNAMICS

Source: the author's own elaboration, 2023

Finally, despite obvious differences in context, all four cases had something in common, they all show that the full inclusion of

both elites and social groups failed for various reasons and that resulted in undermining the prospects of peaceful peacebuilding and reconciliation. ♦

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